

THYROID HORMONE DEFICIENCY AS A CAUSE OF ANEMIA

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Relevance of the Study: Anemia is a clinical and hematological condition characterized by a decrease in hemoglobin levels in the peripheral blood, leading to insufficient oxygen transport to tissues and organs. It can result from various underlying causes, including nutritional deficiencies, chronic diseases, genetic disorders, and hormonal imbalances. One of the factors that have been shown to influence the development of anemia is thyroid hormone deficiency.

Clinical evidence suggests a potential link between anemia and hypothyroidism, a condition where the thyroid gland fails to produce enough thyroid hormones, leading to a slowdown of metabolic processes. Hypothyroidism can cause a reduction in the production of red blood cells, thus contributing to anemia. However, the exact mechanisms behind this connection remain inadequately studied. It is hypothesized that the deficiency of thyroid hormones may impact erythropoiesis, the process by which new red blood cells are produced, or it may interfere with the function of iron, a crucial component of hemoglobin in red blood cells. The relationship between hypothyroidism and anemia is complex, and while studies suggest an association, more research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms at play and to develop appropriate clinical guidelines for managing both conditions simultaneously. Understanding the pathophysiology of how thyroid hormone deficiency leads to anemia could aid in creating more effective prevention and treatment strategies for patients suffering from both hypothyroidism and anemia.

Objective of the Study: To explore the relationship between the development of anemia and thyroid hormone deficiency in patients with hypothyroidism.

Materials and Methods: A comparative analysis of statistical data from patients suffering from anemia in the context of hypothyroidism was conducted. This article presents the results of an examination of 125 patients with hypothyroidism and 54 healthy women in the control group. The study revealed that the level of quality of life in hypothyroidism is significantly lower than among healthy individuals.

Results: The study considered 3 different types of anemia and their respective mechanisms of development. Normochromic anemia occurs due to reduced erythropoiesis activity caused by thyroid hormone deficiency, which is the most common type. Hypochromic anemia is a result of iron deficiency in the human body. The cause of iron deficiency is a lack of the studied hormones, which influence the mechanism of its absorption. The rarest type of anemia in hypothyroidism is hyperchromic anemia, which develops due to a deficiency of vitamin B12 and folic acid. Achieving a high level of quality of life is one of the main tasks in the treatment of chronic diseases. Based on information about the quality of life, it is possible to optimally adjust the patient's treatment plan, including the impact on the psycho-emotional sphere. The features of the quality of life of patients with hypothyroidism are currently an insufficiently studied aspect. The above indicates the need to study such a parameter as quality of life in hypothyroid patients. This article presents the results of an examination of 125 patients with hypothyroidism and 54 healthy women in the control group. The study revealed that the level of quality of life in hypothyroidism is significantly lower than among

healthy individuals. The features of the quality of life were also revealed depending on the age of the patients and the severity of hypothyroidism.

Conclusion: Thus, anemia is a relatively common manifestation of hypothyroidism, as thyroid hormones directly affect the hematopoietic system (one of the consequences of which is anemia). Different ways to prevent the development of anemia are considered, but one of the most effective methods may be supportive and hormonal therapy.

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